

C-ALKYLRESORCINOLS. PART IV NUCLEAR METHYLATION OF 4-ACYLRESORCINOLS.

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The nuclear methylation of various 4-acyl-resorcinols, *viz.*, respropiophenone, resbutyrophenone, 2:4-dihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone and 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone has been studied.

Respropiophenone on nuclear methylation affords 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxypropio-phenone, demethylation of which affords 2:4-dihydroxy-3-methylpropio-phenone which is identical with the ketone prepared by the application of the Hoesch reaction to 2-methylresorcinol and propionitrile. Kostanecki acetylation of the nuclear methylated ketone affords 7-methoxy-2:3:8-trimethylchromone. Similarly the nuclear methylation of the other 4-acylresorcinols has been studied

In connection with our work on "γ-substitution in the resorcinol nucleus" (Shah and Shah, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1939, 132, 300, 949) it was found necessary to synthesise 2-methyl-4-alkylresorcinols by an unambiguous method. It was thought of interest to investigate the nuclear methylation of various 4-acylresorcinols, *viz.*, respropiophenone, resbutyrophenone, 2:4-dihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone and 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone.

Respropiophenone on nuclear methylation by the method of Robinson and Shah (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, 1491) affords a ketone whose constitution as 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxypropio-phenone (I, R=C₂H₅) has been established as follows: (i) The ketone (I, R=C₂H₅) on demethylation affords 2:4-dihydroxy-3-methylpropio-phenone, identical with the compound obtained by the Hoesch reaction on 2-methylresorcinol and propionitrile. Kostanecki acetylation of the ketone (I, R=C₂H₅) with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride affords 7-methoxy-2:3:8-trimethylchromone (II, R'=CH₃), whose constitution is established by its hydrolysis with alkali to 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxypropio-phenone and 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzoic acid (Shah and Laiwalla, *J. Chem. Soc.*, 1938, 1828; Perkin, *ibid.*, 1895, 67, 993).

Resbutyrophenone similarly affords 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybutyrophenone (I, R = C₃H₇), demethylation of which gives 2:4-dihydroxy-3-methylbutyrophenone, identical with the ketone prepared from 2-methylresorcinol and butyronitrile. Kostanecki acetylation of the ketone (I, R = C₃H₇) with sodium acetate and acetic anhydride affords 7-methoxy-2:8-dimethyl-3-ethylchromone (II, R = C₂H₅) whose constitution has been established by its alkaline hydrolysis to 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybutyrophenone and 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzoic acid.

2:4-Dihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone similarly affords 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenylbenzyl ketone (I, R = CH₂Ph), demethylation of which gives 2:4-dihydroxy-3-methylphenylbenzyl ketone, identical with the ketone prepared from 2-methylresorcinol and benzyl cyanide. The ketone (I, R = CH₂Ph) on Kostanecki acetylation gives 7-methoxy-2:8-dimethylisoflavone (II, R' = Ph).

Kostanecki and Tambor (*Ber.*, 1895, 28, 2305) obtained by the nuclear methylation of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone 2:4-dihydroxy-3-methylbenzophenone and 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzophenone. The same substances were prepared by Jones and Robertson (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1932, 1689) by the Hoesch reaction of 2-methylresorcinol and benzonitrile and subsequent methylation of the ketone obtained. Kostanecki and Tambor (*loc. cit.*), however, have given no experimental details. We have isolated on nuclear methylation of 2:4-dihydroxybenzophenone only 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzophenone, demethylation of which affords 2:4-dihydroxy-3-methylbenzophenone, identical with the compound prepared by Jones and Robertson. Acetylation of 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzophenone affords 7-methoxy-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin.

EXPERIMENTAL.

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxypropiofenone (I, R = C₂H₅). — Potassium hydroxide (27.5 g., 4 mols.) was dissolved in methanol (110 c. c.) and respropiofenone (20 g.) was added. The mixture was cooled in a freezing mixture and methyl iodide (85.5 g., 5 mols.) was added all at once with shaking. If two layers separated homogeneity was restored by the

addition of more methyl alcohol. The temperature was then gradually allowed to rise, when potassium iodide separated. Next day the mixture was refluxed for 6 hours. The methanol was removed and the dark solid residue was acidified and filtered. It was then macerated with sodium hydroxide solution (200 c.c., 5%). The insoluble 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-methylpropiofenone crystallised from alcohol in colourless slender pointed needles (5.2 g.), m. p. 78-79°. (Found: C, 68.1; H, 7.2. $C_{11}H_{14}O_3$ requires C, 68.0; H, 7.4 per cent). It is insoluble in alkali and gives a reddish brown colouration with alcoholic ferric chloride.

Demethylation of 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-methylpropiofenone.—(i) A mixture of 2-hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-methylpropiofenone (1 g.) and aluminium chloride (2 g.) was heated at 135-40° for 3 hours, ice and hydrochloric acid were added and the insoluble solid collected. It was treated with sodium hydroxide solution (50 c.c., 5%) and filtered. The alkaline solution on acidification gave the ketone, 2:4-dihydroxy-3-methylpropiofenone, which crystallised from water in rosy needles, m. p. 128-30°. It did not depress the m. p. when mixed with a sample of 2:4-hydroxy-3-methylpropiofenone prepared by the application of the Hoesch reaction to 2-methylresorcinol and propionitrile.

(ii) 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-methylpropiofenone (1 g.) was dissolved in acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and hydriodic acid (*d* 1.7, 20 c.c.) added drop by drop. The reaction mixture was refluxed at 130-40° for 2 hours. It was poured into a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite (200 c.c.) and the yellow solid which separated out was crystallised from water, m.p. 128-29°, yield 0.6 g.

7-Methoxy-2 : 3 : 8-trimethylchromone (II, $R' = CH_3$).—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxypropiofenone (1 g.), sodium acetate (3 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) was heated at 175-85° for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water (500 c.c.). The chromone crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless slender needles, m.p. 69-70°, yield 0.5 g. (Found: C, 66.2; H, 6.7. $C_{13}H_{14}O_3, H_2O$ requires C, 66.1, H, 6.8 per cent).

Hydrolysis of 7-Methoxy-2 : 3 : 8-trimethylchromone.—A mixture of the chromone (0.5 g.) and sodium hydroxide solution (30 c.c., 5%) was refluxed on a sand-bath for 3 hours. On cooling a substance separated out as colourless, wooly needles, which were identified as 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxypropiofenone by direct comparison. The alkaline solution was acidified and the precipitated acid purified by treatment with sodium bicarbonate. The acid was identified as 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzoic acid (Perkin, *loc. cit.*) by direct comparison.

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybutyrophenone (I, R=C₃H₇).—A solution of resbutyrophenone (22 g.) in methyl alcoholic potash (28 g. of caustic potash in 112 c.c. of methanol) was cooled to 0° and methyl iodide (88 g.) added all at once with shaking. Next day the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 hours, filtered from the insoluble potassium iodide and kept in a frigidaire for 2 days. The yellow-crystalline solid that separated out was washed with sodium hydroxide solution (100 c.c., 5%). It crystallised from alcohol in colourless rectangular plates, m.p. 82-84°, yield 6 g. (Found : C, 69.0 ; H, 7.8. C₁₂H₁₆O₃ requires C, 69.7 ; H, 8.2 per cent).

2 : *4-Dihydroxy-3-methylbutyrophenone*.—A mixture of the ketone (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and hydriodic acid (20. c.c.) was refluxed at 125-35° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite (200 c.c.). The solution was extracted with ether, the extract washed with aqueous sodium hydroxide (50 c.c., 5%). The alkaline solution on acidification gave 2 : 4-dihydroxy-3-methylbutyrophenone which crystallised from water as straw-coloured needles, m.p. 155-57°, yield 0.4 g. It did not depress the m.p. of a sample prepared by the application of the Hoesch reaction to 2-methylresorcinol and butyronitrile.

7-Methoxy-2 : 8-dimethyl-3-ethylchromone (II, R'=C₂H₅).—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybutyrophenone (2 g.), sodium acetate (5 g.) and acetic anhydride (30 c.c.) was refluxed at 180-85° for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water (300 c.c.) and the brownish red oil, which separated, was washed with sodium bicarbonate. It distilled at 173°/6 mm. as a yellow oil which solidified on cooling. It crystallised from alcohol in colourless rectangular prisms, m.p. 43-45°. (Found : C, 67.4 ; H, 7.4. C₁₄H₁₆O₃, H₂O requires C, 67.2, H, 7.2 per cent).

Hydrolysis of 7-Methoxy-2 : 8-dimethyl-3-ethylchromone.—The hydrolysis was carried out as in the case of 7-methoxy-2 : 3 : 8-trimethylchromone. The products, 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybutyrophenone and 2:4-dimethoxy-3-methylbenzoic acid, were identified.

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenylbenzyl Ketone (I, R=CH₂PH).—A solution of 2:4-dihydroxyphenylbenzyl ketone (20 g.) in methyl alcoholic potash (from 20 g. of caustic potash and 80 c.c. of methanol) was cooled to 0° and methyl iodide (62 g.) was added all at once with shaking. Next day the reaction mixture was refluxed for 6 hours. Methanol was removed and the dark brown solid was macerated with sodium hydroxide solution (200 c.c., 4%). The insoluble 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenylbenzyl ketone crystallised from alcohol in colourless prisms, m.p. 110-11°, yield 10 g. (Found : C, 75.1 ; H, 6.3. C₁₆H₁₆O₃ requires C, 75.0 ; H, 6.3 per cent).

2 : 4-Dihydroxy-3-methylphenylbenzyl Ketone.—A mixture of the above-mentioned ketone (3 g.), acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) and hydriodic acid (30 c.c.) was refluxed at 125-35° for 2 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite (200 c.c.) and the yellow solid was crystallised from benzene (charcoal) as colourless needles, m.p. 157-59°, yield 1·8 g. The m.p., after admixture with a specimen prepared by the application of Hoesch reaction to 2-methylresorcinol and benzyl cyanide, was not depressed.

7-Methoxy-2 : 8-dimethylisoflavone (II, R'=Ph).—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxyphenylbenzyl ketone (3 g.), sodium acetate (6 g.) and acetic anhydride (30 c.c.) was refluxed at 175-85° for 8 hours. The reaction mixture was poured into water (300 c.c.). The isoflavone crystallised from dilute methanol in colourless needles, m.p. 140-42°, yield 1·5 g. (Found : C, 77·0 ; H, 5·6. C₁₈H₁₆O₃ requires C, 77·1 ; H, 5·7 per cent).

2-Hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzophenone.—A solution of 2 : 4-dihydroxybenzophenone (20 g.) in methyl alcoholic potash (21 g. of caustic potash in 84° c.c. of methanol) was cooled to 0° and methyl iodide (66 g.) was added. The product was isolated in the usual manner. 2-Hydroxy-4-methoxy-3-methylbenzophenone crystallised from alcohol in yellow rectangular prisms, m.p. 125°, yield 6 g. Jones and Robertson (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 125°.

2 : 4-Dihydroxy-3-methylbenzophenone.—A mixture of the preceding ketone (1 g.), acetic anhydride (10 c.c.) and hydriodic acid (15 c.c.) was refluxed at 125-35° for 2 hours. The mixture was poured into a saturated solution of sodium bisulphite (200 c.c.) and the reddish yellow solid was crystallised from dilute alcohol, m.p. 177°, yield 0·6 g. Jones and Robertson (*loc. cit.*) give m.p. 177°.

7-Methoxy-4-phenyl-8-methylcoumarin.—A mixture of 2-hydroxy-3-methyl-4-methoxybenzophenone (1 g.), sodium acetate (2 g.) and acetic anhydride (20 c.c.) was refluxed at 180-90° for 1 hour. The reaction mixture was poured into water (300 c.c.). The coumarin crystallised from dilute alcohol in colourless slender needles which changed into prisms, m.p. 94-95°, yield 0·5 g. (Found : C, 71·9 ; H, 5·7. C₁₇H₁₄O₃, H₂O requires C, 71·8 ; H, 5·6 per cent).